

Original Research

Enterprise Growth in Rural Tanzania: Comparative Analysis between Kilolo and Iringa Districts Voluntary Financial Saving Groups

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Abstract

This study performed comparative analysis of enterprise growth among enterprises owned by members of voluntary financial saving groups (VFSGs) between Kilolo and Iringa districts in rural Tanzania. A sample of 262 members of VFSGs owning enterprises were selected proportionately from various strata. Semi-structured questionnaire was developed and used in collecting quantitative data, in-depth interview and focus group discussions were applied in collecting qualitative data. Analysis of qualitative data was carried out using content analysis. Chi-square was performed to establish association among variables under the study. Further, independent samples t-test was performed for comparative analysis of enterprise growth among enterprises owned by members of VFSGs between Kilolo and Iringa districts. The findings on association among variables were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) with size of the effect being small shown by correlation coefficients (Phi and Cramer' V coefficients < 0.30). Findings from t-test on the amount of money saved, age of members of VFSGs and number of employees were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Further, the association among education level and skills gap, loan defaulting and entrepreneurial education statistically were significant ($p < 0.05$). Intervention programmes through training on entrepreneurial education as capacity building is recommended to be undertaken in both districts with first priority in Kilolo district.

Keywords: Comparative analysis, enterprise growth, Kilolo and Iringa districts, rural Tanzania, voluntary financial saving groups.

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Introduction

Globally, the concern for enterprise growth is pronounced everywhere for business sustainability. For example, in Finland, Timo *et al.* (2024) narrated that enterprise growth results from owners' intention to grow and networking with other firms. This means that, for enterprises to grow remarkably, there must be growth intention within owners which acts as a stimulant towards desired intention. In USA, the government has taken initiatives to allocate adequate fund to support small businesses to access capital through loan, already in the financial year 2023, the federal procurement already awarded 12.1% of its budget to support disadvantaged small businesses to access capital (The White House Washington, 2024). This report from US informs that unless small businesses get sound capital access they will hardly grow, that is why the US government became concerned with high commitment. In Us, government's efforts to through capital support to small businesses is vital given the fact that the statistics on formation of new businesses every month is growing, a total of 28,166 new businesses were formed in June 2024, equivalent to an increase by 0.9% from those formed in May 2024 (United States Census Bureau, 2024). This means that, the newly formed and other existing businesses require growth and sustainability, this is always achieved through sound access to capital.

In Africa, Mulibana and Tshikovhi (2024) established that rural firms in South Africa entirely were dependent on government financial support and networks from actors, in case such supports are withdrawn, a number of them collapse. The research recommended that entrepreneurship education through training should be provided to such firms as capacity building to enable them to operate independently and sustainably. This recommendation exposes that entrepreneurship education is gateway for innovations and exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities geared to sustainable enterprise growth, and it is a way to bridge skills gap that exist among owners of firms. In rural South Africa, another study of Donga and Chimucheka (2024) established that rural women owned firms were challenged with inadequate sources of financing, education and entrepreneurial training, biased gender, limited skills to operate businesses and complicated ways to handle simultaneously business and family responsibilities. These findings connote that rural entrepreneurs seriously need entrepreneurial education to curb skills gap persisting and position them in a better angle that paves the way towards growth.

In Tanzania, despite the importance of rural entrepreneurship in improving peoples' livelihood, it is obvious that in comparison with urban entrepreneurship, the rural one is confronted with various impediments. The study of Mashenene (2020) uncovered that the performance of businesses owned by urban women was three times higher than that of rural owned women as it was presented by the mean score difference. Further, the study exposes that low level of education, family roles which are not balanced, inadequate business information, limited role models, limited control of business finance, limited credit access and the society's attitude being not supportive. Numerous efforts have been dedicated by the government of Tanzania to guarantee economic empowerment of communities in rural areas. The efforts have been directed towards improving services in education, water and sanitation, health, financial, electricity, infrastructure and communication. The government investment made in rural areas is geared towards

creating enabling environment to promote rural entrepreneurship which subsequently promote growth of rural enterprises.

In spite of the government commitment to promote rural entrepreneurship, the statistics according to FSDT (2016) show that there is only eight percent (8%) of people participating in VFSGs in Iringa region, the proportion which is the lowest of all regions in Tanzania followed by Tanga region with 15% of people engaged in VFSGs. Other regions in Tanzania with low number of people participating in VFSGs are Kusini Unguja with 24%, Kilimanjaro with 27% and Mtwara with 38% though comparatively Mtwara region is above the overall 37% of people participating in VFSGs in Tanzania. Regions with high number of people participating in Tanzania are Dar es Salaam being the first region in Tanzania with 98% of citizens involved in VFSGs followed by Lindi with 95%, Kagera 78%, Tabora 66%, Singida 62% and Kusini Pemba 54%. The lowest number of participants in VFSGs in Iringa region formed academic interest to carry out the research. The study of FSDT (2016) was undertaken covering a number of region but it could not carry out comparative analysis of enterprise growth of enterprises owned by members of VFSGs between Iringa and Kilolo Districts. Further, the study of Majenga *et al.* (2024) focused on challenges and practices in promoting rural entrepreneurship in Iringa region but the research was holistic as it did not perform comparative analysis of enterprise growth between Iringa and Kilolo districts. The research therefore focused to answer this research question, to what extent does enterprise growth of members of VFSGs between Iringa and Kilolo districts differ? The results from this research will provide policy implication to prioritize in designing intervention programmes given scarcity of available resources.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature Review

Hofstede in 2003 developed a theory (model) which presents national culture with the focus of five cultural dimensions that help to provide cultural differences. These cultural dimensions are Power Distance Index, Uncertainty Avoidance Index, and Long-Term Orientation versus Short-Term Orientation and masculinity/femininity. The Power Distance Index is concerned with the extent to which the less powerful organizations' members acknowledge and assume that unequal distribution of power exists. This hints that the level of inequality in the society is backed by the followers as much as by the leaders. The Uncertainty Avoidance Index is concerned with tolerance of the society against situations with ambiguity. This means that, members of VFSGs from Iringa and Kilolo districts are subjected towards situations with ambiguity in ensuring that growth of enterprises is realized. Long-Term Orientation versus Short-Term Orientation which are concerned with values in association with Long Term Orientation which are perseverance and carefulness; in the focus of the current research, owners of enterprise are required to observe high level of perseverance for them to ensure high level of enterprise growth. On the other hand, Short Term Orientation values are concerned with respecting traditions, fulfilment of societal obligations and protecting face of individuals, implying that social network through established and operating VFSGs, members fulfil societal obligations. Other cultural dimensions under Hofstede theory include Masculinity and Individualism.

In the focus of this research, measuring of entrepreneurial culture was fitted in the five cultural dimensions of Hofstede theory i.e., the culture of members of the VFSGs is responsible in spearheading cohesiveness among members and consequently resulting into enterprise growth. The questions of interest to be answered are; how does power distance among members of VFSGs influence entrepreneurial intention and consequently enterprise growth? How does uncertainty avoidance among members of VFSGs influence entrepreneurial intention and consequently enterprise growth? How does masculinity/femineity influence entrepreneurial intention and consequently enterprise growth? How does long-term orientation such as goal setting influence entrepreneurial intention and consequently enterprise growth? How does individualism/collectivism of members of VFSGs influence entrepreneurial intention and consequently enterprise growth? In this view, entrepreneurial culture was operationalized into five dimensions whose measurements were embedded into Hofstede cultural theory. Looking further education as one of cultural components, entrepreneurship education was operationalized to mean members of VFSGs need entrepreneurial education for improved operations and hence improved enterprise growth. It is should be further noted that, operationalization and measurements of entrepreneurial education was defined in a similar way with entrepreneurial culture under application of Hofstede cultural theory. The departure of the current research from the Hofstede cultural theory is that the five cultural dimensions have been looked at national level while for current case the focus was at Iringa region with focus of Iringa and Kilolo administrative districts. Various previous researches that have attempted to make use of cultural dimensions have used Hofstede theory to draw up the variables under the study (Kamwela, 2024; Mashenene, 2016).

The variables that were derived from the theory were entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial culture, practices under operations of VFSGs were not part of the Hofstede theory, meaning that the second theory was added to fill the gap. The Resource Based Theory was considered appropriate to cover the gap on practices adopted by VFSGs. Wernerfelt (1984) founded the Resource Based theory which pinpoints that competitive advantage of a firm over competitors is basically the derivative of the firm's internal resources and capabilities The said resources in the context of this research are viewed as fundamental parameters for the firms' uniqueness and success. The adoption of this theory was appropriate since such practices are treated as important inputs for the firm's operations. The practices under this research were size of loans provided, monthly savings made by members, rate of loan defaulting and interest rates charged to borrowers. These practices as valued resources were broadly defined under this study to reflect capabilities of VFSGs' members to execute enterprise profitable activities. This theory interprets VFSGs as resources with high value embedded in firms' operations geared to enterprise growth. Several former studies that adopted this theory in commonality to this study addresses more or less similar concepts about resources which are highly valued, such studies are practices adopted by VFSGs as important resources (Majenga *et al.*, 2024), capabilities and strategic management under dynamic environment (Teece, Pisano & Shuen, 1997), linkages between enterprises' resources and competitive advantage (Barney, 1991) and culture and winning strategic markets (Barney, 1986). It is from this theory, the practices under focus were size of loans provided, savings from VFSGs members, rate of loan defaulting and interest rates charged to borrowers.

Empirical Literature

Rural entrepreneurship is vital for the development of rural people in the world. Ambasta and Satpathi (2023) in India established that rural entrepreneurship is important for rural enterprise formation and growth that lead to job creation. Despite rural enterprises struggle to realize growth, they face challenges of human right resources, access to financial resource, shortage of skills and training, as the result, the intended growth is hardly realized. The report of NC IDEAS Foundation and MDC Rural Prosperity & Investment (2024) pointed that rural entrepreneurship at North Carolina in US requires direct investment to address stunted growth resulting from financial capital limitation. This means that, rural entrepreneurship has a great chance to flourish in rural Us if funding challenge is well addressed. Further, it was pinpointed that that entrepreneurs in rural US own fewer financial resources compared to those in urban, they also experience scarcity of specific skills due to limited training programmes (Endeavor, 2021; Belson, 2020).

In African countries, Otuokere (2021) informed that the achievement of rural development will be realized only through rural entrepreneurship, which has been the solution to unemployment, improved productivity and reduced rural urban migration in Nigeria. In the same connection with previous presented studies, it is evident that rural entrepreneurship should be taken seriously by different actors, and the efforts should continuously be made to empower rural entrepreneurs through entrepreneurial education that will consequently shape their practices and close skills gap that emerge in the course of business operations. The study of Muriithi (2024) pointed out that transforming rural areas in Central Kenya required serious skill development, that is capacity building through training. On the other hand, it was established that rural entrepreneurship in Nigeria is confronted with limited access to funds, meaning that the growth of rural entrepreneurship in Nigeria will hardly be realized unless funding as a stumbling block is resolved (Nwanko and Okeke, 2017). Furthermore, in South Africa found that rural entrepreneurship is faced with low level of education, inadequate training, business skills, financial literacy and funding, suggesting that such situations will continue suffering unless strategic measures are developed for curb the challenges (Utete and Zhou, 2024; Donga and Chimucheka, 2024).

Enterprise growth in Tanzania is also traced from various scholars whereas the variables extracted from the theories were taken as focal points. The study of Kamwela (2024) in Tanzania SMEs found that entrepreneurial opportunities exploitation and power distance as the cultural dimension were exhibited a positive and significant relationship. At the same time, the same study exposes that the correlation association of entrepreneurial opportunities exploitation and power distance were collectively mediated with innovation of actors, meaning that enterprise growth is the function of favourable entrepreneurial culture. In the view of the related research, cultural capital was noticed to be a pivotal in inspiring enterprise growth (Lutz *et al.*, 2021), proposing that societies that consider cultural phenomena as important variables and integrate them into their working operations, such societies achieve the planned activities, in the case of this research, realization of enterprise growth.

Another construct under the study was entrepreneurial training which was learnt as the cornerstone of SMEs sustainability in Tanzania whereas SMEs were found have skills gap in various areas including keeping business records, customer service and identification of business opportunities (Malipula, 2023). The findings from this research inform that entrepreneurship education offered through training empowers business operators, as the result they acquire competencies in searching for profitable business opportunities and consequently leading to enterprise growth. The study of Mbura and Minja (2022) came out with findings that despite the importance of entrepreneurship trainings to SMEs, the lack systematic model of delivery and focus on key ingredients to enable trainees to become creative and innovative. These findings suggest that entrepreneurship education through training should continue being provided but right training models should be adopted to be results-based training that focus on empowering training to be creative and innovative. Entrepreneurship training was earmarked as if successfully undertaken it helps to unveil business opportunities to SMEs, meaning that it leads to increased sales and correspondingly profits (Iganile, 2019).

Enterprise growth is measured using numerous indicators, some are qualitative while some are quantitative. For quantitative measurements, Slavik *et al.* (2023) employed sales as the measurement of enterprise growth, a similar study of Ismail (2022) employed sales as one of constructs in measuring SMEs growth. In another perspective, John *et al.* (2023) measured firms' performance in terms of growth in sales, profitability, return on assets (ROA) return on investment (ROI). In another focus, capital increase has been used by various studies to measure performance of SMEs (Mashenene and Kumburu (2020; Mashenene, 2019, Mashenene, 2016, Maziku *et al.*, 2014; Tundui, 2012). In measuring SMEs growth, Ismail (2022) employed sales among other constructs, the findings in the view of the current study, capital was chosen to be the measure of enterprise following the fact that several studies under review indicated that capital was used to measure firm's performance.

Research Methods

Research design

The research adopted two types of research designs that were performed serially. At the beginning, the study carried out an exploratory case study with the purpose of capturing insight of the subject matter about the practices undertaken by VFSGs in the study areas. According to Yin (2014), an exploratory case study research design is a qualitative study aiming at collecting detailed information about something being studied. Qualitative data were collected with the aim of supplementing quantitative data that formed the main part of the study. Further, a survey research design was adopted in the second phase whereas a semi-structured questionnaire was developed to collect quantitative data, Mashenene (2016) and Majenga (2013) adopted similar research designs.

Sample size and sampling procedures

The research was undertaken in Iringa region which was selected purposefully based on the region being ranked the least in terms of users of VFSGs with only 8% of users of

VFSGs countrywide (FSDT, 2016). In comparison, Tanga region was the second least region to Iringa region with 15% of users of VFSGs countrywide (FSDT, 2016). In this view, Iringa region was purposefully selected since the study focused on empowerment of enterprises of owned by VFSGs. Further, purposive sampling technique was adopted to select Iringa and Kilolo Districts given the fact that the two districts formed the rural districts in Iringa region. The selection criteria for districts were based on the districts being rural and with the highest population. Following these criteria, Iringa district has the highest population of all with 315,354 people followed by Mufindi district with the population of 288,996 and Kilolo district being the third with the population of 263,559 people (URT, 2022). However, during selection of districts, Mufindi district was eliminated since it is the district, which is semi-urban, in this regard, Iringa and Kilolo districts qualified for the selection based on the criteria that they are the mostly rural with the highest population among rural districts in Iringa region (URT, 2022; FinScope, 2017). Further, purposive selection of two wards Kalenga and Ifunda in Iringa district was performed that was followed by selection of Mibikimitale and Udumuka villages in Ifunda ward and from Kalenga ward Kalenga and Isaka villages were selected. Furthermore, two wards from Kilolo district, Nyalumbu and Irole wards were selected purposefully that whereas Ilula Sokoni and Ilula Mwaya villages were selected from Nyalumbu ward and Lundamatwe and Irole villages were selected from Irole ward. In this regard, this made a total sum of eight villages being purposefully selected in four wards of Kilolo and Iringa districts.

The population of the study was formed by the users of VFSGs owning enterprises in Iringa and Kilolo districts. Several strata of users of VFSGs owning enterprises existed, such strata formed a population of the study whose lists were collected from village leaders. A sample size (n) of 384 Sample size was drawn from the strata using proportionate stratified sampling that was followed by random selection. The formula developed by Cochran (1997) (equation 1) was adopted to estimate a sample size (n):

$$n = Z^2pq/e^2 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Whereby: Z = confidence level = 1.96 at 95% confidence interval, n = sample size, p = proportion in the largest population = 50%, q = 1-p and e = margin of error accepted = 0.05. Therefore,

$$n = \frac{1.96^2}{0.05^2} * \frac{0.5 * 0.5}{1} = 384.$$

Data collection methods

Primary data were collected whereas the response rate of questionnaire returned was 262 (68.23%) out of 384 total number of questionnaire administered. It was revealed that some questionnaires were not collected since some of them were not returned and some respondents were not found at their enterprises where questionnaires were dropped. Formulation of the questionnaire was undertaken using questions with 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree) aiming at capturing data regarding practices for managing VFSGs. The variables for the practices adopted by VFSGs included skills gap, standardization, actions taken to loan defaulters, entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention. Adoption and modifications of questions in the questions was in accordance with FinScope (2017),

Mashenene (2016), FSDT (2016) and Liñán *et al.* (2011). The same questionnaire also consisted of questions capturing continuous data about age of respondents (years), average amount of money saved per month (TZS), loan size (TZS), time taken by members of VFSGs to access loan (days), interest rate charged to borrowers (%), capital invested (TZS) and number of employees (persons). Data regarding practices of VFSGs such as amount of savings (TZS), size of loans provided (TZS), interest rates (TZS), amount of loan default (TZS) and measurement of enterprise growth (TZS) captured as continuous data.

Before commencement to data collection, installation of KoBo Toolbox software in data collectors' mobile phones was carried out that was followed by entering the questionnaire into the KoBo software that is useful in maximizing reliability of data and it captures geographical coordinates at different locations during data collection. To ensure validity of the questionnaire, before commencement of data collection pre-testing of the questionnaire was undertaken in Dodoma, some revisions and improvements were made after pretesting. Training of research assistants was carried out with the purpose of familiarizing with data collection instruments. To enhance validity of data, multiple data collection and analysis methods were adopted. Cronbach Alpha test was performed to test reliability of the data.

Data analysis

Content analysis was performed to analyze qualitative data whereas at the first stage data preparation was carried out that was followed by familiarization of data and initial coding. Thereafter, formulation of categories was undertaken that was followed by refining of data and selection of codes. Further, analysis of patterns and themes was performed whereas identification of new themes and recognition of patterns and relationships was carried out. Presentation and interpretation of findings was undertaken whereas meaning was extracted from codes and were integrated with respective themes for effective communication of findings.

Analysis of quantitative data was undertaken using an analytical tool, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Cross tabulation was performed involving education level of members of VFSGs and current practices adopted by VFSGs. The current practices adopted by VFSGs consisted of skills gap, standardization, actions taken against loan defaulting, entrepreneurial education, entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial culture. During cross tabulation, Pearson Chi-square values, p-values and Fisher's Exact Test values were generated and presented. All practices that produced insignificant values of Chi-square were dropped, therefore, only skills gap, actions taken against loan defaulting and entrepreneurial education whose Chi-square values were significant were presented and discussed. Fisher's exact test was performed since it is the exact measure of association while Chi-Squared test is based on approximation (Kim, 2017). Further, Phi coefficients were generated to measure direction of the association among variables while Cramer's V on the other hand was computed to test size of the effect in the associations established. According to Cohen (1988 as cited in Pallant, 2016), the coefficients of Phi lie between 0 and 1 whereas those with higher values expressing stronger association between the two variables, the interpretation is that the coefficient of 0.10 indicates small effect, 0.30 medium and 0.5 large effect. In case of negative

coefficient of Phi connotes inverse association between the variables. In a similar manner, interpretation of Cramer's V values is in harmony with the Phi coefficient (Pallant, 2016). According to Pallant (2016), the coefficient of Phi is appropriate for 2 by 2 tables in crosstabs whereas on the other hand, for tables greater than 2 by 2 Cramer's V suits accordingly. Therefore, in the current study, both Phi and Cramer's coefficients were adopted whereas for crosstab involving education level and skills gap dummy (Table 1) and education level and loan defaulter dummy (Table 2) Cramer's V was adopted. For the crosstab involving entrepreneurial culture dummy and loan defaulter dummy (Table 3) and entrepreneurial education and loan defaulter dummy (Table 4) Phi coefficient was applied.

For comparative analysis, independent samples t-test was performed comprising of age of members of VFSGs (years), amount of money saved/savings per month (TZS), loan size (TZS), time taken to access loan (days), interest rate (%), capital invested (TZS) and number of employees (persons). Independent samples t-test was performed following the fact that members of VFSGs from the two districts operate independently, hence, differences can easily be established (Mashenene, 2020; Mashenene, 2019; Pallant, 2016). As the analytical requirement for independent samples t-test, tests for Levene for equality of variance, normality and outlier were performed before performing t-test.

Size of the effect

For variables whose t-test results were significant; age of respondents, amount of money saved (savings) and number of employees, computation of Eta Squared was undertaken with the aim of estimating size (magnitude) of the mean difference in enterprise growth variables between Kilolo and Iringa districts. According to Cohen (1988) a good measure of magnitude of the effect of mean difference between groups under comparison is the Eta Squared. Computation of the Eta Squared was achieved using equation 4 as suggested by Cohen (1988).

$$EtaSquare = \frac{t^2}{t^2 + (N_1 + N_2 - 2)} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Whereby:

t = computed t- statistics

N₁, N₂ = sample size for the members of VFSGs in Kilolo and Iringa districts.

Interpretation of Eta squared values as the statistical measurement of the magnitude of the effect of dependent variable ranges from 0 to 1, it provides representation of the percentage of variance in the dependent variable as it is described by independent groups, for this case, the Kilolo and Iringa districts. The Eta Squared value of 0.01 connotes small sized effect, 0.06 moderate sized and 0.14 large sized effect (Cohen,1988).

Findings and Discussion

Tests for Associations among Variables

Education level * skills gap dummy crosstabulation

Table 1 presents findings for crosstabulation between respondents' education and skills gap dummy. The findings indicate that members of VFSGs had primary education which formed the highest proportion with 60.3% followed by 33.2% with secondary education. This position of the highest proportion of respondents having primary education inform existence of skills gap which was also consistent with the results in Majenga *et al.* (2024). Further, crosstabulation results statistically indicate significant association between education level and skills gap ($\chi^2 = 13.114$, $p = 0.004$), meaning that skills gap exists among members of VFSGs. In this regard, such members are confronted with skills gap in executing their day-to-day operations of VFSGs and enterprises. To ascertain size of the effect of the association, Cramer's V coefficient = 0.224 was opted, signifying that effect size was small (Cohen, 1988).

Table 1. Education level * Skills gap dummy crosstabulation (n=262)

Education_level	Percent	Skills gap dummy		Total
		0.00	1.00	
Primary	Count	67	91	158
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	42.4%	57.6%	100.0%
	% within Skills gap dummy	67.0%	56.2%	60.3%
	% of Total	25.6%	34.7%	60.3%
Secondary	Count	24	63	87
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	27.6%	72.4%	100.0%
	% within Skills gap dummy	24.0%	38.9%	33.2%
	% of Total	9.2%	24.0%	33.2%
Certificate	Count	9	4	13
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	69.2%	30.8%	100.0%
	% within Skills gap dummy	9.0%	2.5%	5.0%
	% of Total	3.4%	1.5%	5.0%
Diploma	Count	0	3	3
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Skills gap dummy	0.0%	1.9%	1.1%
	% of Total	0.0%	1.1%	1.1%
Degree	Count	0	1	1
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Skills gap dummy	0.0%	0.6%	0.4%
	% of Total	0.0%	0.4%	0.4%
Total	Count	100	162	262
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	38.2%	61.8%	100.0%
	% within Skills gap dummy	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	38.2%	61.8%	100.0%

(Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 13.114$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.004$), (Fisher's Exact test = 12.422, $p = 0.005$), (Phi = 0.224), Cramer's V = 0.224)

Education level * loan defaulter dummy crosstabulation

The findings in Table 2 statistically indicate presence of association between education level and loan defaulting practice ($\chi^2 = 11.114$, $p = 0.012$), apprising that the two variables cross tabulated were associated. The results under these variables are closely related to a large extent with high number of members of VFSGs having primary education. It is evident that capacity building in the form of entrepreneurship and business will help to enhance loan recovery and reduce the number of loan defaulters. Further, the correlation coefficient (Cramer's $V = 0.206$) pictures the existence of small sized effect as interpreted in Cohen (1988). These findings fall in line with those of Majenga et al. (2024) which exposed that low level of education among members of VFSGs accelerated the rate of loan defaulting among them in Iringa and Kilolo districts.

Table 2. Education level * loan defaulter dummy crosstabulation (n=262)

Education_level	Percent	Loan defaulters dummy		Total
		0.00	1.00	
Primary	Count	81	77	158
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	51.3%	48.7%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	55.5%	66.4%	60.3%
	% of Total	30.9%	29.4%	60.3%
Secondary	Count	57	30	87
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	65.5%	34.5%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	39.0%	25.9%	33.2%
	% of Total	21.8%	11.5%	33.2%
Certificate	Count	4	9	13
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	30.8%	69.2%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	2.7%	7.8%	5.0%
	% of Total	1.5%	3.4%	5.0%
Diploma	Count	3	0	3
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	2.1%	0.0%	1.1%
	% of Total	1.1%	0.0%	1.1%
Degree	Count	1	0	1
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	0.7%	0.0%	0.4%
	% of Total	0.4%	0.0%	0.4%
Total	Count	146	116	262
	% within EDUCATION_LEVEL	55.7%	44.3%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	55.7%	44.3%	100.0%

(Pearson Chi-Square (χ^2) = 11.114, $df = 4$, $p = 0.012$), (Fisher's Exact test=12.697, $df = 4$, $p = 0.015$), (Phi=0.206), Cramer's $V = 0.206$)

Entrepreneurial culture dummy * Loan defaulter dummy crosstabulation

The findings in Table 3 statistically indicate presence of association between education level and entrepreneurial culture practice in dummy ($\chi^2 = 6.897, p = 0.009$), describing that the two variables cross tabulated were associated. The results under these variables are closely related to a large extent with high number of members of VFSGs having primary education. It is apparent that capacity building in the form of entrepreneurship and business will prevent loan recovery and minimize the number of loan defaulters. Further, the correlation coefficient ($\Phi = -0.162$) portraying the existence of negative small sized effect as interpreted in Cohen (1988), connoting that as unfavourable entrepreneurial culture increased loan defaulting rate increased correspondingly.

Table 3. Entrepreneurial culture dummy * Loan defaulter dummy crosstabulation (n=262)

Entrepreneurial culture dummy	Percent	Loan defaulters dummy		Total
		0.00	1.00	
0.00	Count	63	69	132
	% within Entrepreneurial culture dummy	47.7%	52.3%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	43.2%	59.5%	50.4%
	% of Total	24.0%	26.3%	50.4%
1.00	Count	83	47	130
	% within Entrepreneurial culture dummy	63.8%	36.2%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	56.8%	40.5%	49.6%
	% of Total	31.7%	17.9%	49.6%
Total	Count	146	116	262
	% within Entrepreneurial culture dummy	55.7%	44.3%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	55.7%	44.3%	100.0%

(Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 6.897, df = 1, p = 0.009$), (Fisher's Exact test $p = 0.009$), ($\Phi = -0.162$), Cramer's $V = 0.162$)

Entrepreneurial education dummy * Loan defaulter dummy Crosstabulation

The findings in Table 4 statistically indicate presence of association between education level and loan defaulting practice ($\chi^2 = 4.333, p = 0.042$), imparting that the two variables cross tabulated were associated. The results under these variables are closely related to a large extent with high number of members of VFSGs having primary education. It is stated that capacity building through entrepreneurial education will alleviate loan recovery and minimize the number of loan defaulters. In connection, the correlation coefficient ($\Phi = -0.129$) illustrates the existence of negative small sized effect as interpreted in Cohen (1988), meaning that as entrepreneurial education

diminishes loan defaulting increases. These findings fall in line with those of Majenga *et al.* (2024) which exposed that inadequate entrepreneurial education existed among members of VFSGs in the Iringa and Kilolo districts.

Table 4. Entrepreneurial education dummy * Loan defaulter dummy crosstabulation (n=262)

Entrepreneurial education dummy	Percent	Loan defaulters dummy		Total
		0.00	1.00	
0.00	Count	81	79	160
	% within Entrepreneurial education dummy	50.6%	49.4%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	55.5%	68.1%	61.1%
	% of Total	30.9%	30.2%	61.1%
1.00	Count	65	37	102
	% within Entrepreneurial education dummy	63.7%	36.3%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	44.5%	31.9%	38.9%
	% of Total	24.8%	14.1%	38.9%
Total	Count	146	116	262
	% within Entrepreneurial education dummy	55.7%	44.3%	100.0%
	% within Loan defaulter dummy	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	55.7%	44.3%	100.0%

(Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 4.333$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.042$), (Fisher's Exact test $p = 0.042$), (Phi = -0.129), Cramer's $V = 0.129$)

The qualitative findings established from qualitative data provide supplementary to quantitative findings as follows.

“... the SINAI Group in Iringa district with 88 members operates under two groups, group A with 50 members and group B with 38 members. The receives business training from the Emmanuel International under the Pentecostal Holiness Church, the foundation that has helped to some extent to keep members focused on business. On rotational basis, members of the group also make arrangement to visit nearby groups to learn practices how they operate their businesses and VFSGs at large...” [FGD session with SINAI Group members held on 30th May 2023].

“...The Mama Wasasa Group in Iringa district is operated with 23 members but has received no training on business since it was founded five years back. The group owns and operates catering services, but inadequate business skills limit quick growth of the enterprise...” [FGD session with Mama Wasasa GROUP members held on 30th May 2023].

“...The Mshikamano Group with 10 members was founded in 2007 in Kilolo district, the group is engaged in keeping pigs, milk cows and

cultivation of maize and sunflower for business. The group since founded to date, has received no raining on entrepreneurship and business skills. This has been a major limiting factor to exploit emerging entrepreneurial opportunities...” [FGD session with Mshikamano Group members held on 24th May 2023].

“...Jiwezeshe group in Kilolo district is operated with 28 members. Since founded, the group has remained with only one source of income generating activity, i.e. lending money to its members at an interest of 10% per month. Lack of diversification in sources of income generating activities is the result of inadequate entrepreneurial education and business skills whereas the group has never received any kind of training on business skills and entrepreneurship, the situation which limits growth efforts...” [FGD session with Jiwezeshe Group members held on 24th May 2023].

Independent Samples t-test

Testing assumptions for t-test

Normality

Statistically, normality denotes distribution of data which is the basic assumption for the measurement of the variation among variables. The normality assumption is important in case generalization of the results is expected to cover the whole population Field (2013). Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk are the main inferential tests that assess numerically normality. These tests make comparison of data normality to normal distribution and provide guidance for objective based judgments. For the sample size larger than 200, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is appropriate while Shapiro-Wilk test is suitable for sample size ranging from 50 to 2,000. In this view, both Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk satisfied the underlying assumptions and were suitable for the current study provided that the sample size was 262. The findings in Table 5 express that the results for Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk indicate that variables subjected to the tests were significantly different ($p < 0.000$) from normal distribution, meaning that the variables under tests were not normally distributed, hence, violating the assumption for normality. Statistically for large simple sizes, the results for Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk are anticipated statistically to be significant Pallant (2016), however, Abbasi (2011) pointed out that such significant results cannot be interpreted as data deviated from normal distribution. Therefore, data under this study were considered suitable for independent samples t-test in respect to the tests of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk.

Table 5. Normality test

Variables	Districts	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Age (years)	Iringa	0.132	90	0.001	0.951	90	0.002
	Kilolo	0.106	110	0.004	0.953	110	0.001
Amount of money saved (TZS)	Iringa	0.170	90	0.000	0.831	90	0.000
	Kilolo	0.185	110	0.000	0.846	110	0.000
Loan size (TZS)	Iringa	0.303	90	0.000	0.544	90	0.000
	Kilolo	0.272	110	0.000	0.479	110	0.000
Time to access loan (Days)	Iringa	0.412	90	0.000	0.323	90	0.000
	Kilolo	0.425	110	0.000	0.370	110	0.000
Interest rate (%)	Iringa	0.482	90	0.000	0.244	90	0.000
	Kilolo	0.492	110	0.000	0.182	110	0.000
Capital invested (TZS)	Iringa	0.324	90	0.000	0.573	90	0.000
	Kilolo	0.279	110	0.000	0.567	110	0.000
Number of employees (persons)	Iringa	0.309	90	0.000	0.777	90	0.000
	Kilolo	0.340	110	0.000	0.659	110	0.000

Test of outliers

Given sensitivity of t-test to outliers, data were subjected to be teste for outliers before data analysis was carried out. The results emanated from variables under test (age of respondents, amount of money saved and number of employees) between Iringa and Kilolo districts demonstrated that data were normally distributed, meaning that outliers were absent.

Levene's test for equality of variance

Table 6 presents Levene's test results that was used to make assessment of the assumption for the population variance homogeneity from which samples were selected. The test of Levene is applicable before interpretation of t-test results. Lawson (2014) pointed out that the test is responsible for testing the assumption that equal variances exist. According to Vogt (2005) the major concern for carrying out this test is that a t-test is invalid if this assumption is unmet. The results in Table 3 shows that the levels of significance of the Levene's test were 0.821 for age, 0.778 for loan size, 0.600 for time taken to access loan, 0.916 for interest rate charged and 0.517 for capital invested, the values being greater than the pre-determined cut-off of 0.05, therefore, the assumption of equal variances was not violated. Therefore, t-values were reported from the first line of the table, meaning that equal variances assumed were reported (Pallant, 2016). On the other aspect, the levels of significance for amount of money saved (0.009) and number of employees (0.003) which were less than the established cut-off point of 0.05, necessitated alternative t-values to be reported from the second line of the table, hence, equal variances not assume were reported to make compensation of the differences in the two t-values and brings about equal meaning in interpretation (Pallant, 2016).

Table 6. Levene's test

Variables	Variances	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Sig.
Age (years)	Equal variances assumed	0.051	0.821
	Equal variances not assumed		
Money saved (TZS)	Equal variances assumed	6.929	0.009
	Equal variances not assumed		
Loan size (TZS)	Equal variances assumed	0.080	0.778
	Equal variances not assumed		
Time to access loan (Days)	Equal variances assumed	0.276	0.600
	Equal variances not assumed		
interest rate (%)	Equal variances assumed	0.011	0.916
	Equal variances not assumed		
Capital invested (TZS)	Equal variances assumed	0.420	0.517
	Equal variances not assumed		
Employees (persons)	Equal variances assumed	8.741	0.003
	Equal variances not assumed		

T-test independent samples results

Age

The comparison using age of owners of VFSGs (Table 7) show that the mean age between Iringa and Kilolo districts were 40.6093 years for Iringa district and 37.2183 years for Kilolo district. The notable difference in age between the two groups signifies that VFSGs members were of the age of youth though those from Kilolo were younger than those from Iringa district by a mean difference of 3.391, suggesting that those from Iringa district had much higher sense of saving due to higher age difference. These results sound in a similar way with those in Majenga *et al.* (2024) which established that the overall mean age of VFSGs owners in the two districts was 38.8 years which was the age for youth with several family responsibilities.

Table 7. Independent samples t-test results

Variables	District	n	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error Mean	t-value
Age (years)	Iringa	120	40.6093	10.77290	1.31481	2.578**
	Kilolo	142	37.2183	10.45837	1.31810	
Money saved (TZS)	Iringa	120	43,316.67	38309.358	3890.352	2.304**
	Kilolo	142	34,119.72	26503.441	3991.631	
Loan size (TZS)	Iringa	105	820,048.08	1283471.847	189133.220	0.191
	Kilolo	128	783,877.34	1550517.627	185662.707	
Time for loan (days)	Iringa	114	2.88	5.347	0.643	-0.213
	Kilolo	139	3.01	4.869	0.649	
Interest rate (%)	Iringa	114	11.05	6.274	0.872	-0.197
	Kilolo	138	11.22	7.362	0.859	

Variables	District	n	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error Mean	t-value
Capital (TZS)	Iringa	120	1,036,166.6667	1770175.10093	214490.04045	0.332
	Kilolo	137	964,956.2044	1666193.93189	215353.00208	
Employees (persons)	Iringa	116	1.9828	1.25790	0.14676	2.431**
	Kilolo	131	1.6260	1.04760	0.14839	

Notes: ** signify level of significance at 5%

Savings

The findings in Table 7 indicate a difference in amount of money saved by members of VFSGs per month between Iringa and Kilolo district whereas for Iringa district the mean amount was TZS 43,316.67 compared to the mean of TZS 34,119.72 for Kilolo district, implying that savings per month for Iringa district was higher than that of Kilolo by a mean difference of TZS 9,196.95 equivalent to 26.95%. These findings show close relationship with those in Majenga *et al.* (2024) which informed that the mean saving for the two districts was TZS 38,332.06 per month, implying than VFSGs in Iringa district operate above the mean while those of Kilolo operate below the mean, this means that prioritization in terms of capacity building should be first directed to Kilolo district followed by Iringa district.

Loan size

The findings in Table 7 indicate that average loan size for Iringa district was TZS 820,048.08 compared to TZS 783,877.34 for Kilolo district, implicating a meagre mean difference of TZS 36,170.74 for Iringa district being higher than that of Kilolo district. These findings seem to be connected with the mean savings for Iringa districts which were higher than that of Kilolo district. These findings provide responses to the recommendations by Majenga *et al.* (2024) that required comparative analysis between the study areas.

Time taken to access loan

The findings in Table 7 show that average time taken by members of VFSGs in Iringa district was 2.88 days while for Kilolo district was 3.01, meaning that members of VFSGs from Iringa district received loans at shorter time compared to their counterpart in Kilolo Iringa. This situation can be the result of little savings received at Kilolo district that would necessitate to accumulate some savings for a longer period of time before disbursed to loan applicants, the case would be different for Iringa district that suggests liquidity to meet its obligations as indicated by shorter period of time in issuing loans to its members. These findings provide answers to Majenga *et al.* (2024) that recommended comparative analysis of enterprise performance between the study areas was required.

Interest rates

The findings in Table 7 show small difference of mean interest charged for a loan between Iringa and Kilolo districts whereas for Iringa district is 11.05% while for Kilolo is 11.22%, such small difference in interest rate might be due to loan documents prepared in the same locality with shared information. Though there is slight difference between

the two interest rates, for Kilolo district is higher than that of Iringa district by 0.17%, this small difference adds up burden to borrowers and consequently would contribute to lower enterprise growth compared to those from Iringa district.

Number of employees

The findings in Table 7 indicate that difference in number of employees exist between enterprises owned by VFSGs in Iringa and Kilolo districts whereas for Iringa district the mean was 1.9828 persons while for Kilolo district was 1.6260 being less by the mean of 0.35 persons from that of Iringa district. These findings indicate the connection with the amount of money saved by members of VFSGs between Iringa and Kilolo districts whereas Iringa district demonstrated higher savings than Kilolo district. These findings are in line with the recommendations that comparative analysis between the study areas was deemed necessary Majenga *et al.* (2024).

Size of the effect

Table 8 presents computed results of Eta Squared whereas for age, amount of money saved and number of employees. The results indicate that all values of Eta Square were 0.01, meaning that the effects for all variables were small (Pallant, 2016; Cohen, 1988).

Table 8. Summary of Eta Square value

Variables	Eta Squared values	Interpretation
Age (years)	0.01	Small effect
Amount of money saved (TZS)	0.01	Small effect
Number of employees (persons)	0.01	Small effect

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from this research is that respondents' education level was found statistically associated with skills gap and loan defaulting ($p < 0.05$) with small effect as marked by Phi coefficient < 0.3 . This conclusion alerts that there is close association between education level and skills gap, empirically, 60.3% of respondents had primary education, suggesting that they had inadequate entrepreneurial and business education which posed skills gap which consequently resulted into amplified loan defaulting practice among members of VFSGs. The conclusion on the same further entails that the association between entrepreneurial culture and loan defaulting and entrepreneurial education and loan defaulting statistically were significant ($p < 0.05$) with small sized effect (Phi coefficient < 0.3). Further, the results of independent samples t-test necessitate to conclude that respondents' age, savings made by members of VFSGs and number of employees in enterprises owned by members of VFSGs between Iringa and Kilolo districts exhibited statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) with small sized effect as denoted by Eta Squared value of 0.1 and Iringa district being somehow better than Kilolo district as shown by higher mean differences. The findings further lead to the conclusion that though capital invested by enterprises owned by members of VFSGs between Iringa and Kilolo districts was statistically insignificant, the difference existed as shown by the

mean differences whereas Iringa district demonstrated higher capital invested than Kilolo district, meaning that Kilolo would be proposed to be the first district for intervention between the two followed by Iringa district.

Recommendations

The recommendations are made to the Institute of Rural Development Planning (IRDP) to collaborate with the Iringa and Kilolo district councils and other partners in development to collectively formulate capacity building programmes geared to provide training on entrepreneurial and business education to members of VFSGs. Through this capacity building programme, knowledge gap demonstrated by existence of skills gap, inappropriate entrepreneurial culture and inadequate entrepreneurial education will be closed, hence, resulting to minimal number of loan defaulters. It is from these research findings that an opportunity for IRDP is opened up for quick intervention through its Corporate Social Responsibility (SCR) budget and solicitation of funds from the respective LGAs and donors. The recommendation further is made to areas for future research to scale up the research to other rural areas in different regions of Tanzania with low number of people participating in VFSGs; Tanga, Kusini Unguja, Kilimanjaro and Mtwara to establish status of similar situations.

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